

bandy - an interactive performance system

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Abstract. *bandy is an interactive performance system that lets participants play a simple game to collectively create music on real musical instruments over the internet. Players can join together on a video chat application to see and hear the band of acoustic, electric, and electronic instruments respond in real time.*

1. Motivation

Figure 1. bandy web application

Over the past few years I've moved geographically further away from my friends and musical collaborators. I was missing making music with them and looking for ways to play music remotely. Our past year spent inside has given me the opportunity to experiment with some new available internet technologies and see how they could be used to maintain the sense of connecton and the joy of discovery in playing and improvising together.

As a composer I explore stochastic and chance determination of the traditional elements of music, pitch, duration, dynamics, and tempo, within controlled systems. The aesthetic choices of composition are then ones of level of control over the stochastic processes, sources and qualities of sound, density of musical information, performance, and interaction. I combine these elements into systems which define individual pieces of music; often using novel physical and digital interfaces.

Groups of performers can be used as random event generators in such a musical system. They exert influence over the resulting sounds but not control. In bandy, performers' actions determine the density of events but they don't have direct choice over the notes or the instruments on which those notes are performed. Those are instead determined by the compositional parameters and machine learning algorithms. Performers are then free to play within the system and create music without the need for specific musical training. We all, composer, performers, and audience, are surprised by the results. This form of playful music generating is inspired by historic, indeterminate, compositional processes (Cage, Xenakis, etc.) as well as complex emergent systems as in Céleste Boursier-Mougenot's from here to ear series.

2. System Description

Figure 2. bandy system diagram

A set of simple mobile web games allow players to influence the creation of a musical composition by bouncing a ball against colored boxes. Each time a box is hit it generates an event that is collected in a real-time database and sent to a piece of software that acts as a performance controller. The performance controller uses Magenta machine learning libraries' Piano Genie to create musical information based on the events from players' games. Aggregated events from all players are translated into note sequences by the algorithm, which has been trained on 1400 western classical piano compositions. These note sequences are represented in MIDI format and can be filtered and sent to a set of controllable instruments. My choice and design of instruments and application of filtering and audio effects create specific compositions. The band of instruments can be viewed via video conference so players can see and hear the music they are creating in real time and interact with their bandmates.

The number of players can have a significant effect on the musical result. Limitations are intentionally imposed by the game mechanics allowing many players to

interact at the same time while keeping the musical result varied and dynamic. There are moments when the system breaks out of its western harmonic patterns and modulates seemingly at random or breaks into a streaming cadenza when a player's ball gets stuck between blocks and creates a flurry of events. It is the balance and contrast between these two states that is the artistic goal.

Players can access bandy using modern web browsers on mobile or other computer platforms at <http://www.bandy.camp>

References

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